

**Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some
N-Substituted-benzenesulphonamides Pendant
with 2-Thio-1,3,4-oxadiazoles, 3-Mercapto-
4-phenyl-1,2,4(H)-triazoles**

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VARIOUS derivatives of oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles, triazoles and 4-aminobenzenesulphonamides are known to exhibit various biological activities¹. Hence it was thought of interest to synthesise the benzenesulphonamides with pendant oxathiadiazoles and triazoles with a view that these molecules may possess the synergistic fungicidal activity. Herein we report the synthesis of the title compounds (5-9) from the common intermediate 4.

The common key intermediate, acetic acid [*N*-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl) benzenesulphonamido-4-oxy]-3-hydrazide (4) was prepared by reacting hydrazine hydrate with ethyl [*N*-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzenesulphonamide-4-oxy]acetate (3) in alcohol. Compound 3 was obtained by reacting 4-hydroxy-*N*-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzenesulphonamide (2) with ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone and anhydrous K₂CO₃; 2, in turn was obtained by the diazotisation followed by hydrolysis of readily available 4-amino-*N*-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzenesulphonamide (1). On cyclisation with CS₂ in alcoholic KOH, compound 4 yielded the final product 5, and similarly on treatment with 4-substituted-phenyl isothiocyanate followed by refluxing with alkali afforded the compounds 6-9 in good yields (Scheme 1). The structural assignments of all the compounds were based on elemental analysis (C, H, N), ir and nmr spectral data. In nmr spectra, the proton of SO₂NH in all compounds appeared as broad singlet at δ 8.2-9.0 which was D₂O exchangeable.

Fungitoxicity: The antifungal activity of the compounds 5-9 and 4-aminobenzenesulphonamide was evaluated against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium oxysporium* by adopting the usual agar plate technique² at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations using commercial dithane M-45 as the standard.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) Diazotization, H₂SO₄, water, (ii) ethyl chloroacetate, anhydrous K₂CO₃, (iii) NH₂NH₂, (iv) CS₂, alcoholic KOH, (v) 2N NaOH, R-C₆H₄-NCS (*p*).

The percentage of inhibition with respect to the standard was calculated by measuring the zone of inhibition at the interval of 24 h upto 96 h of incubation. All the results were the mean values of triplicates.

A comparison of the fungitoxic data of the compounds 5–9 with their parent molecule (i.e. 4-

aminobenzenesulphonamide) reveals that the former possess better fungicidal activity (90%) than the latter (40%) at 100 ppm level. This implies that the presence of two active moieties like benzenesulphonamide pendant with isoxazole, oxadiazole or triazole in the same molecule as in 5–9 worked better than in the former which contains only one active moiety, amino benzenesulphonamide. Further, 5–9 were also found to possess better fungicidal activity than the standard dithane-M-45, particularly at 100 ppm level (82%) as against (90%) observed in the former. The highest activity (72%, 94%) was, however, observed in 7 among all the compounds at 10 and 100 ppm concentrations probably due to the presence of C₁ group at *para*-position of the triazole nucleus.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R./G.R. grades (E. Merck/Aldrich) unless otherwise specified. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 267 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

4-Hydroxy-N-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzenesulphonamide (2): A solution of 1 (2.52 g, 10 mmol) dissolved in concentrated H₂SO₄ (5 ml) was cooled to 0°. To it was added NaNO₂ solution (0.69 g, 10 mmol), stirred well for 0.5 h at 0–5°, and the yellowish solution obtained was added to boiling sulphuric acid-water (1:1) mixture and then cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from hot water to get yellowish needles (48%), m.p. 144–46°; ν_{\max} 3 400 (OH), 3 240 (SO₂NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 350 and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); δ 8.5–8.2 (2H, br s, SO₂NH and OH, D₂O exchangeable), 7.4–6.9 (5H, m, ArH) and 1.6 (3H, s, CH₃).

Ethyl[N-(5-methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzene sulphonamido-4-oxy]acetate (3): To a solution of 2 (0.508 g, 2 mmol) in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g, 4.3 mmol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.25 g, 2.1 mmol) was added gradually and the contents were refluxed for 22 h. It was then concentrated and the residue was added to cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethyl acetate as yellowish crystals (71%), m.p. 68–69°; ν_{\max} 3 160 (SO₂NH), 2 940–2 900 (O–CH₂), 1 760–1 750 (COOEt), 1 600 (C=N), 1 360, 1 150 (SO₂), 1 260 and 1 080 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); δ 7.8–7.3 (5H, m, ArH), 5.20 (2H, s, OCH₂), 2.05 (3H, t, *J* 5 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃) and 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃).

[N-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzene sulphonamido-4-oxy]acetic acid hydrazide (4): A mixture of an ethanolic solution of 3 (0.68 g, 2 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (99%; 3 ml) was refluxed for 8 h and then concentrated and cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from 50% alcohol as white crystals

(77%), m.p. 199–201°; ν_{\max} 3 360 (NHNH₂), 3 210 (SO₂NH), 2 970 (OCH₃) 1 680 (C=O) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 8.8–8.5 (4H, br s, NHNH₂ and SO₂NH), 7.5–7.1 (5H, m, ArH) and 5.0 (2H, s, OCH₃).

5-[N-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzene sulphonamido-4-oxymethyl]-2-thio-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5): To an ethanolic KOH solution (5 ml) of **4** (0.65 g, 2 mmol) was added CS₂ (2 ml) gradually. The contents were refluxed for 18 h until the evolution of H₂S ceased. The reaction mixture was concentrated and then 5% HCl was added. The resulting solid was recrystallised from 50% alcohol as greyish white crystals (75%), m.p. 140–41°; ν_{\max} 3 220 (SO₂NH), 2 880 (OCH₃), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 250 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 9.1–8.9 (2H, br s, NH, SO₂NH), 7.3–6.8 (5H, m, ArH), 4.9 (2H, s, OCH₃) and 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃).

5-[N-(5-Methyl-3-isoxazolyl)benzene sulphonamido-4-oxymethyl]-3-mercapto-4-(4-substituted-phenyl)-1,2,4(H)-triazole (6–9): To an alcoholic solution of **4** (0.65 g, 2 mmol), phenyl isothiocyanate (0.27 g, 2 mmol) was added and the contents were refluxed for 4 h, then concentrated and the residue obtained was refluxed with 2N NaOH (5 ml). It was cooled, acidified and the resulting solid was recrystallised from 50% alcohol: **6** (yellowish white crystals, 66%), m.p. 152–54°; **7** (61%), m.p. 165–67°; **8** (68%), m.p. 158–60°; **9** (64%), m.p. 172–74°; ν_{\max} 2 590 (SH), 1 610 (C=N), 1 350 and 1 150 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); δ 8.7 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 7.5–6.6 (10H, m, ArH), 6.35 (1H, br s, SH) and 1.8 (3H, s, CH₃).

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